

A Surface Mass Ejection (SME) from Betelgeuse

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Abstract

The sequence of spectroscopic and photometric measurements and diagnostics preceding, during, and following the Great Dimming of Betelgeuse (2019 – 2020), gives evidence of a large surface mass ejection (SME) from the photosphere of the supergiant star. This outburst and its immediate effects spanned more than a year, and now in 2023, the star is still recovering from the event, entering year 5 of the disturbance and its consequences. This phenomenon was observed intensively for the first time - and represents an additional process of mass loss from luminous stars.

1 Introduction

The red supergiant Alpha Orionis (Betelgeuse), one of the brightest stars in the sky exhibits brightness and velocity variations generally with two typical periods: 420 days and a longer ~ 2000 day period. The shorter 400-day variation is attributed to the fundamental pulsation mode (Joyce *et al.* 2020) whereas the cause of the longer period variation is not known for certain. Its brightness has been documented since 1840 (AAVSO Archive) and for almost two centuries, the star has appeared brighter than a visual magnitude of ~ 1 . Surprisingly, in 2019 December, Betelgeuse was approaching its usual minimum of the 400-day period, when it continued to get fainter - substantially fainter by early February 2020. It reached a minimum value of 1.6 visual magnitude, and then began to recover (Fig. 1).

Betelgeuse has long been a target for intensive imaging and spectroscopic studies from the ground and from space. Because it is a supergiant and close by, the photospheric diameter of 42 mas, and the more extended chromosphere - reaching 3 to 4 times the optical radius - allows resolution of the stellar surface with ultraviolet imaging and interferometric techniques. During the years 2019-2022, many techniques were used to observe the star. A brief timeline of the observations will be given here, which provides insight and documentation of the direct measurement of a massive surface mass ejection (SME) from the photosphere. This event, originating in the southern hemisphere of the star moved out through the extended atmosphere, left the photosphere in a cooler state and changed the subsequent optical and radial velocity variation of the supergiant. Critical observations along a time line are discussed in the following sections. An extended more detailed discussion and additional measurements can be found in Dupree *et al.* (2022).

2 2019 January – April

Optical interferometric images of Betelgeuse in 2019 January gave the appearance of a roughly symmetric image of the star's surface (Montargès *et al.* 2021). However, during this time, optical spectra at high spectral resolution from the star as a whole were subjected to a tomographic technique

(Kravchenko *et al.* 2021). This powerful technique models the photosphere and identifies the level where a line is formed within the photosphere. Thus, the velocities of the absorption lines yield the dynamic structure of the photosphere. Kravchenko *et al.* (2021) identified a strong shock in the line of sight, and the onset of expansion within the photospheric layers through 2019 March.

During this time (and subsequently as well), continuous monitoring of the radial velocity of Betelgeuse from optical echelle spectra made with STELLA (Granzer *et al.* 2021), revealed that the photosphere (as a whole) began expansion in 2019 January, and this expansion remained roughly constant at about 7 km s^{-1} for ~ 200 days.

Spatially resolved ultraviolet emission spectra from HST obtained in 2019 April gave no indication of anomalous behavior. Since these ultraviolet features generally arise from the chromosphere, its normal appearance is not surprising. Betelgeuse is a large star, and plasma with a velocity of $5\text{-}10 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ would travel a distance of $0.1 R_*$ in 3 to 6 months, assuming a radius of $1000 R_\odot$ (Ohnaka *et al.* 2011; Harper *et al.* 2017). Thus we would not expect to detect a chromospheric event until several months after the disruption in the photosphere.

3 2019 September – December

Spatially resolved ultraviolet spectra obtained during 3 visits of HST spanning 2019 Sept 18 - Nov. 28 revealed substantially enhanced Mg II and continuum emission over the southern hemisphere of the photosphere and beyond (Dupree *et al.* 2020). Profiles of the Mg II doublet suggested mass outflow had occurred. Electron density diagnostics of C II indicated that the flux enhancement in the southern hemisphere contained higher electron density of plasma. Slightly lower photospheric temperatures at this time were suggested by near-IR photometry (Guinan *et al.* 2019). At the end of 2019 December, optical imaging with VLT/SPHERE/ZIMPOL revealed a substantial darkening of the southern hemisphere of the star (Montargès *et al.* 2021).

4 2020 January – February

Throughout 2020 January, the star continued to dim, reaching an historically faint value of $V \sim 1.6$ from 2020 Jan 27 – Feb 13. During this time, Betelgeuse was observed with many instruments because the astronomical community and the public were intensely interested and concerned about its unusual behavior. TiO diagnostics suggested a photospheric temperature decrease (Kravchenko *et al.* 2021; Harper *et al.* 2020; Levesque & Massey 2020). A meteorological satellite, Himawari, indicated the increased presence of O-rich circumstellar dust around the star (Taniguchi *et al.* 2022). The optical absorption spectrum became weak (Fig. 2), suggesting a photospheric temperature decrease as well (Dupree *et al.* 2022). However, the chromospheric fluxes, as observed by HST, had returned to 'normal' on 2020 Feb. 9, and no substantial enhancement of these fluxes occurred during 2020 extending to 2022 April.

Thus the cumulative effect of the photospheric shock, the ejection of material from the photosphere that traversed the chromosphere, eventually created molecules and dust in the outer atmosphere when conditions were right. The photosphere was left in a cooler and less dense state.

5 A Surface Mass Ejection

This surface mass ejection (SME) appears to have been caused by the confluence of an extended photospheric outflow and presumably a large surface convective cell inferred from the shock motions in the photosphere. Solar coronal mass ejections (CME) involve predominantly hot coronal material and are typically associated with solar flares - a magnetic phenomenon (Tian *et al.* 2021). After the CME, the structure of the resulting corona can change with a drop in the coronal temperature and a decrease in the density (Vanninathan *et al.* 2018). Many characteristics of mass ejections differ between the Sun and a star like Betelgeuse (see Table 1).

The solar example suggests that magnetic fields might be given more consideration than previously thought. Weak variable fields have been found in Betelgeuse (Mathias *et al.* 2018), although there is no high temperature plasma, no X-rays, and no record of any brief flaring phenomena. Thus it may be a challenge to assess the presence and/or effects of magnetic fields in causing an SME.

6 The Recovery

After the Great Dimming, both the magnitude variation and the radial velocity of Betelgeuse changed substantially (Fig. 3). The 400-day period exhibited by the V-magnitude disappeared, and was replaced by changing short term oscillations of low amplitude and erratically ranging from ~ 100 to 200 days. Currently (in early 2023), it may be returning to the fundamental mode, but the star has surprised us in the past.

The amplitude of the photospheric velocity variations decreased substantially, from its behavior earlier in 2019-2020, Granzer *et al.* (2023) in this volume presents a more extensive velocity history of the star extending back to 2009, and their wavelet analysis of the radial velocity behavior suggests that frequency of the fundamental mode may be slightly varying.

The SME appears to have created a photosphere that is still (in 2023) attempting to return to its normal state. For-

tunately, the AAVSO members continue to monitor this star, the STELLA observations are continuing, and spatially resolved HST visits are planned into early 2024.

Other luminous stars, such as VY CMa exhibit signatures of episodic mass loss via clumps in the interstellar medium (Humphreys and Jones 2022). And several other luminous stars have shown dimming behavior similar to Betelgeuse with the formation of dust (Bedding *et al.* 2002; Goldman *et al.* 2022). Theoretical evolutionary models including episodic mass loss in red supergiants give good agreement with the numbers of high luminosity supergiants in other galaxies and the Magellanic Clouds (Massey *et al.* 2023). Betelgeuse offers a unique opportunity to probe and understand such episodic behavior.

7 References

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Table 1: Characteristics: SME versus CME

Characteristic	SME	CME
Timescale	Months	Minutes
Size	$0.3 R_{\text{star}}^2$	$0.01 R_{\text{star}}^2$
Relative Mass lost	10^9	1
Frequency	Years?	Weekly
Cause	Convection+pulsation	Magnetic/flaring

Figure 1: V-magnitudes as measured by photoelectric photometry with values from the AAVSO archive. From Dupree *et al.* 2020.

Figure 2: A section of the optical spectrum from TRES/FLWO showing the substantial weakening of the photospheric line months before and during the Great Dimming. Such weakness is characteristic of a decrease in effective temperature of the photosphere. The change in relative depth of the V I and Fe I lines also implies a temperature decrease (Dupree *et al.* 2022).

Figure 3: The V-magnitude and the radial velocity as measured from 2018 to 2023. The broken curve in the top panel marks the 400-day period. The broken curve in the radial velocity panel (*below*) marks the 2169 day period based on the ephemeris of Granzer *et al.* (2023). The AAVSO photoelectric measures were made by T. Calderwood, and O. Nickel (NOT). The DC magnitudes were obtained by D. Carona. STEREO magnitudes were measured from the images of the NASA STEREO spacecraft.